

UV CURING OF NON-TRANSPARENT FIBRE REINFORCED PLASTICS IN LIQUID COMPOSITE MOULDING PROCESSES

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ABSTRACT

This research presents an innovative approach that combines ultraviolet (UV) radiation curing with Liquid Composite Moulding (LCM) to enable a fast, energy-efficient, and digitally controllable manufacturing process for glass and carbon fiber-reinforced plastics. Conventional curing of fiber-reinforced polymers (FRPs) involves long cycle times and high temperatures, leading to elevated energy demand and tooling inefficiencies, which this work aims to overcome by targeting faster, more energy-efficient processes in line with industry needs for lightweight design, sustainability, and cost reduction [1,2]. To characterize the quality of the manufactured composites with non-transparent fibers, four-point bending tests, tensile tests, and fiber volume fraction (FVF) measurements were performed. In addition, the degree of crosslinking was analyzed, and microscopic imaging was conducted to evaluate the fiber-matrix interaction. All samples were produced using the developed UV-RTM tool, where the cavity is transparent for the UV irradiation. The bending tests showed minimum and maximum forces of 300 Pa and 320 Pa while the tensile tests yielded ultimate loads ranging from 170 MPa to 270 MPa. The degree of cross-linking across the layer thickness was measured and had an average of 84 %. These tests were carried out for two different materials. Pure glass fiber (GF) samples served as reference samples for the samples with embroidered non-transparent carbon fiber (CF). Overall, this study demonstrates the potential of UV-based curing in LCM processes to enable a scalable, cost-effective, and sustainable manufacturing method for high-performance composite parts.

1 INTRODUCTION

Fiber-reinforced polymer composites have become a foundational material system in aerospace, automotive, and wind energy sectors due to their high specific strength, corrosion resistance, and design flexibility [3]. In the field of FRP manufacturing, conventional thermal curing processes still predominate. These methods rely on high temperatures and long processing times, making them energy-intensive and often associated with significant demands on tooling and thermal management [4]. As an alternative, UV-assisted curing is gaining increasing attention.

UV curing, an alternative method widely used in the coating and printing industries, offers rapid polymerization through radical photoinitiation [5]. While UV curing has been applied to glass fiber composites, carbon fiber's opacity poses a significant barrier to deep matrix polymerization.

Radical UV curing processes also face significant challenges that must be addressed to ensure effective polymerization. A major issue is oxygen inhibition, where the presence of oxygen interferes with the radical polymerization reaction, leading to incomplete curing at the material surface. To overcome this, curing typically needs to be performed in closed or inert environments, which complicates the process design. Alternatively, novel tooling solutions must be developed that allow sufficient UV light penetration while maintaining the necessary environmental control. Additionally, the use of non-transparent fibers poses further limitations, as their opacity prevents effective UV transmission through the composite, restricting the achievable curing depth and uniformity.

Considering these factors, this research focuses on investigating a UV-cured composite manufactured

via the LCM process, with particular attention to how variations in process parameters affect the degree of cure and mechanical properties, while aiming for a time- and energy-efficient production method that meets industry demands for lightweight construction, cost efficiency, and sustainability.

Achieving energy-efficient and cycle time-optimized curing of FRP using UV requires its integration into LCM processes and subsequent optimization. Several interdependent parameters must be considered to realize this goal. To effectively control these interactions, their influences must be systematically investigated and validated, enabling a stable and controllable process.

For good material properties, UV-intransparent CF is integrated into the process and cured. To date, it has only been possible to cure GF up to a maximum thickness using UV radiation, depending on the set process parameters and process technology. The maximum achievable thickness is influenced by the fiber volume content, the type of reinforcement fibers, the resin chemistry, and the characteristics of the UV emitter [6].

A special focus is placed on the UV-curing of CF, integrated through the Tailored Fiber Placement (TFP) process in load-path-optimized orientations, as part of the overall process development and the characterization of the resulting composite material [7]. Critical process parameters such as FVF, resin chemistry, fiber type, and emitter characteristics are investigated to develop a reliable and controllable curing system. Since UV curing does not require thermal energy input to initiate or complete polymerization, heating of thermally inert molds is no longer necessary.

This work investigates the feasibility of UV curing for carbon fiber-reinforced composites using LCM processes. Key questions include whether sufficient crosslinking can be achieved within and beneath the carbon fiber roving and whether the resulting laminates exhibit acceptable mechanical performance.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Materials

All samples were produced using the resin system RAYLOK® C1100 from Allnex GmbH (Drogenbos, Belgium) in combination with a glass fiber fabric (600 g/m²) supplied by R&G Faserverbundwerkstoffe GmbH (Waldenbuch, Germany). The composite parts were manufactured using the developed resin transfer molding (RTM) tool with an injection pressure of 2 bar. An embroidered carbon fiber roving (Tenax®-E, HTS40, X030, 12K, 800 tex, V2) was used for a higher stiffness.

The RAYLOK® C1100 resin system is specifically designed for the production of glass fiber-reinforced composites cured by UV radiation. The curing behavior of this system is based on the free-radical polymerization of acrylate and vinyl ester groups, initiated by UV exposure. In contrast to thermally cured epoxy systems, RAYLOK® C1100 is a single-component system offering on-demand curing. It remains stable in its liquid state until UV activation, which then triggers immediate polymer network formation.

The RAYLOK® C1100 resin system is a styrene-free vinyl ester formulation. Its high reactivity under UV radiation enables rapid curing within seconds to minutes, offering a significant reduction in cycle time compared to conventional thermally cured systems. A notable advantage of the system is its long pot life prior to UV exposure (1-K System), which allows for extended processing windows, increased flexibility during layup or infusion, and reduced material waste.

The mechanical performance of the cured system, measured according to standard ASTM protocols, is summarized in Table 1:

Property	Value
Tensile modulus	~2.3 GPa
Tensile strength	~50 MPa
Elongation at break	~2.3 %
Flexural modulus	~2.8 GPa
Flexural strength	~80 MPa
Glass transition temperature (T _g)	~102 °C

Table 1: Material Properties RAYLOK ® C1100 [8].

2.2 Manufacturing of UV-cured composites

The RTM process was employed to manufacture specimens for mechanical characterization, enabling the production of large-scale samples (358 × 258 mm²) incorporating a multilayer glass fiber preform with an embroidered carbon fiber roving. The RTM mold consists of two rigid mold halves, sealed at the parting plane and clamped together with bolts. The cavity is enclosed on both the upper and lower sides by tempered safety glass (ESG), providing transparency for UV curing while ensuring mechanical stability and an effective seal during the infiltration process, see Figure 1. Before processing, the mold is cleaned with isopropanol and air pressure, followed by the application of a release agent (HP7, Marbocote) in three layers with degassing steps between applications. The injection and evacuation hoses are installed afterwards. The injection hose is connected to a pressure vessel, which is later filled by the resin for the infusion process, while the evacuation hose is attached to a resin trap and a vacuum pump.

Figure 1: (a) Explosion view of glass plates and glass plate frame assembly, (b) explosion view of assembled glass plate frames and mold frames, and (c) assembled mold in open (charge) position [9].

The fiber preform is prepared by stacking three layers of glass fiber fabric, onto which a carbon fiber roving is embroidered on one layer of glass fiber using a fine polyester thread (Serafil, 300tex, 10) on a TFP embroidery machine TCWM 102 (Tajima Industries Ltd., Nagoya, Aichi Prefecture, Japan). The embroidered fabric is cut to match the dimensions of the other layers and then positioned within the lower mold cavity (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Embroidered machine TCWM 102 and the RTM tool with prepared Preform

Sealing plugs are installed at the resin inlet and outlet ports, and the mold halves are assembled and clamped. The resin system RAYLOK[®] C1100 is injected under controlled pressure (initially 800 mbar) through the cavity, which is tilted by 45 ° to enhance air evacuation. The infiltration process was continuously adjusted to maintain a constant flow rate as the flow front progressed, resulting in a concave flow front profile due to faster resin movement near the cavity edges, see (Figure 3). The pressure is gradually decreased to 30 mbar by the end of infiltration.

Figure 3: Flow front in the cavity of the RTM mold

Curing was conducted immediately after infiltration by irradiating the entire cavity surface through the transparent mold plate for 120 seconds using an air-cooled MZ80-395 nm UV-LED (IST INTECH Ltd, Banbury, Oxfordshire, United Kingdom), manually positioned close to the mold surface due to the window thickness.

2.3 Material characterization methods

Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FT-IR)

The degree of cross-linking across the laminate thickness is measured using a LUMOS II FT-IR microscope (Bruker Optics GmbH & Co. KG, Ettlingen, Germany), performing measurements at 45 discrete points along the thickness direction of the samples. FT-IR analysis was conducted by comparing the C=C absorption peak intensity before and after UV curing, allowing the degree of conversion to be determined based on the reduction of reactive double bonds.

Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC)

The reaction enthalpy of the resin systems is analyzed using a UV-DSC 3500 Sirius (NETZSCH Group, Selb, Germany). The DSC system measures the exothermic heat flow during UV-induced

curing, enabling the analysis of reaction kinetics, curing rate, and degree of conversion in real time.

Microscopic Analysis

For microscopic analysis of the specimen cross-sections, samples were initially embedded in an epoxy resin (Struers EpoFix Resin, Struers GmbH, Willich, Germany). Subsequent grinding and polishing were performed using a Struers TegraPol-11 polishing machine (Struers GmbH, Willich, Germany). Wet grinding was conducted with diamond suspensions (Struers DiaPro, 3 μm and 9 μm), while final polishing employed alumina suspensions (Buehler MasterPrep, 0.05 μm , ITW Test & Measurement GmbH, Esslingen am Neckar, Germany) applied on appropriate adhesive discs (Struers MD-Plan and MD-Dur for diamond grinding, and Buehler Master Tex MD Rondo for alumina polishing). Microscopic investigations are conducted using a Keyence VHX-7000 digital microscope with the VH-Z20R objective (Keyence Corporation, Osaka, Japan).

Fiber Volume Content Analysis

The specimens were first dried to ensure consistent measurement conditions. For this purpose, they were placed in numbered crucibles and heated in a drying oven (BINDER, BD/ED/FD (E2)) at 70 °C for 24 hours. After drying, the samples were cooled for 15 minutes in a desiccator over silica gel. Once the specimens reached room temperature (23 °C), both the sample and the empty crucible were weighed. (DIN 29971 Sept. 1989)

Subsequently, the specimens were returned to the crucibles and heated at 600 °C for 24 hours in a muffle furnace (Heraus, KM 170, Hanau, Germany). During this process, the cured resin was thermally decomposed, leaving only the heat-resistant glass fibers. The crucibles containing the remaining glass fibers were then transferred to a desiccator to cool to room temperature. Once cooled, the crucibles with the remaining fibers were weighed again.

Mechanical Testing

The tensile properties of the UV-cured samples are evaluated according to DIN EN ISO 527-4 (Type 2) using the Hegewald & Peschke Universal Testing Machine Inspekt 250 kN (Hegewald & Peschke Meß- und Prüftechnik GmbH, Am Gründchen, Germany). The bending tests were conducted according to DIN EN ISO 14125 (Class 1) using the Hegewald & Peschke 20-1 (20 kN) testing machine (Hegewald & Peschke Meß- und Prüftechnik GmbH, Am Gründchen, Germany). The tensile test specimens have dimensions 250 mm \times 25 mm \times 2,6 mm. The 4th point bending test specimens measured 80 mm \times 15 mm \times 2.6 mm. Each specimen type is tested at least seven times. The test setup for the four-point bending and tensile tests is shown in Figure 4 (a-c).

Figure 4: a) Bending test before the test, b) Bending test after fracture failure, c) Tensile testing machine with clamped sample.

3 RESULTS

For the determination of the C=C double bond conversion, cross-sectional samples were prepared in the same manner as for the microscopic analysis. The preparation process ensures consistent positioning and surface quality for accurate spectroscopic measurements. The measurement setup and a representative sample are shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5: On the left, a measurement setup using FT-IR spectroscopy is shown. On the right, a cross-section of a sample is displayed.

Figure 6 illustrates the measurement of C=C double bond conversion in the thickness direction of the GFRP sample. An average conversion rate of 84 % is determined, excluding the top and bottom regions of the sample from the evaluation. A decrease of approximately 10 % is observed at both the top and bottom regions of the sample. This reduction is presumed to result from oxygen diffusion into the RTM mold, which may inhibit polymerization in these areas due to the oxygen inhibition effect in radical curing. To assess the spatial distribution of the conversion, three measurement series were conducted in the thickness direction of the sample. These are represented in green, yellow, and red curves on the right side of the figure, corresponding to different vertical positions within the specimen. The sample is shown in a horizontal orientation, with light exposure applied from the left side ($x = 0.0$ mm). The right side of the figure ($x = 2.4$ mm) represents the bottom surface of the sample. This layout provides a clear depiction of the depth-dependent curing behavior across the composite thickness.

Figure 6: C=C double bond measurement of a GFRP sample, achieving an average value of 84 %.

To investigate the effect of irradiation time on the C=C double bond conversion, four samples containing the 12 K carbon fiber were prepared and subjected to different exposure durations. For the longest irradiation time of 120 seconds, a conversion rate of 84 % is achieved, corresponding to the

reference value obtained without the roving. The nine measurement points were placed above, within, and below the roving to evaluate the curing behavior in its immediate vicinity. (Figure 7)

Figure 7: Sample with embedded C-Roving and marked measurement points used for determining the C=C double bond conversion and the Evaluation of the measuring points with the mean value.

The Table 2 lists the mean values of the respective samples with the corresponding irradiation times:

Sample	Irradiation Duration [s]	Mean value C=C double bonds [%]
A	30	70
B	60	68
C	90	69
D	120	84

Table 2: Measurements of the average value C=C double bonds of the samples with different irradiation times

The FVF and porosity of the seven tested samples are summarized in Table 3. The FVF ranged from 36.07 % to 37.86 %, with a mean value of 36.61 % and a standard deviation of 0.60 %. The corresponding porosity values ranged from -0.85 % to 4.76 %, with an average of 0.48 % and a standard deviation of 1.97 %. Negative porosity values are attributed to measurement uncertainty and indicate negligible or absent pore content in the respective samples.

Sample	Fiber volume content					
	Fiber			Pores		
	FVF	average	Standard deviation	Sample	average	Standard deviation
	%	%	%	%	%	%
CFK 1	36,13	36,61	0,60	0,77	0,48	1,97
CFK 2	36,50			-0,50		
CFK 3	36,67			4,76		
CFK 4	36,64			-0,85		
CFK 5	36,39			-0,55		
CFK 6	36,07			-0,51		
CFK 7	37,86			0,22		

Table 3: Measured fiber volume fractions and porosity values of the tested specimens.

The force-deflection behavior of six specimens under three-point bending is illustrated in Figure 8. All samples exhibit a comparable mechanical response, characterized by an initial linear-elastic region up to approximately 7–8 mm deflection, followed by nonlinear deformation until reaching the maximum force. The fracture loads lie between approximately 300 Pa and 320 Pa, demonstrating good

repeatability and uniformity across the specimens. After reaching the peak load, the force drops abruptly, indicating sudden failure of the specimen. Minor deviations in stiffness and ultimate load may result from local variations in fiber alignment or porosity. Overall, the results confirm consistent flexural performance of the tested composite samples.

Figure 8: Force–deflection curves of six specimens from three-point bending tests, showing consistent peak loads and failure behavior.

Figure 9 presents the force-elongation curves of seven glass fiber specimens, each reinforced with an embroidered roving. The majority of specimens display a linear-elastic response up to failure, typical of fiber-reinforced composite materials. The specimens fail abruptly upon reaching their maximum load, indicating brittle fracture behavior.

Maximum forces range from approximately 170 MPa and 270 MPa, with elongations at failure between 1.0 % and 1.8 %. Specimen 6 achieved the highest load and strain before failure, suggesting improved load transfer or local reinforcement effects due to the roving structure. The similarity among most curves indicates good repeatability and consistency in material behavior and test conditions.

However, specimen 3 deviates significantly from the others, showing almost no force development and a flat response across the strain axis. This anomaly suggests a testing error, misalignment, or possible damage in the specimen before loading. Given this, it should be excluded from the statistical evaluation.

The abrupt force drops after reaching peak load confirm a brittle failure mode, as expected for glass fiber composites. The embroidered roving appears to have contributed positively to the tensile performance, though the scatter in the maximum loads indicates some variability in the stitching or local fiber alignment.

Figure 9: Tensile test results of glass fiber specimens with embroidered roving.

4 CONCLUSIONS AND DISCUSSION

This study investigated the feasibility of UV curing glass fiber-reinforced polymer (GFRP) components, locally stiffened with non-transparent stitched carbon fiber CF, manufactured via LRI processes using UV radiation. Complementary characterization was conducted to assess the degree of cure, the material characteristics, the fiber volume content, and the fiber–matrix interfacial quality.

The highest degree of cure was observed in specimens manufactured via the RTM process after 120 seconds of UV exposure, reaching approximately 84 %. Mechanical testing of RTM-manufactured specimens irradiated for 120 seconds revealed mechanical performance comparable to that of conventionally cured CFRPs. These findings confirm the viability of UV curing for CFRP components under the conditions studied.

However, the samples examined featured a relatively low carbon fiber content. Therefore, the transferability of results to structural CFRP components with higher fiber volume fractions and without glass fibers is limited. Further investigations focusing on preforms made solely from carbon fiber fabrics are recommended to evaluate the broader applicability of UV curing for structural applications.

The UV curing durations in this study were limited to four discrete intervals (30, 60, 90, and 120 s). It is plausible that intermediate exposure times could also yield cure degrees exceeding 84 %. Future research should aim to identify the optimal irradiation time with finer time resolution, particularly to better understand the inflection point in cross-linking behavior within the 90–120 s range.

Cross-sectional analysis showed consistent FVF across all samples, with an average of 36.61 % and minimal variation (standard deviation of 0.60 %). Porosity was generally low, averaging 0.48 %, although some negative values were recorded due to measurement uncertainty, indicating negligible pore content.

Mechanical testing under three-point bending showed highly consistent force–deflection behavior across six samples. Peak loads ranged between 300 Pa and 320 Pa and all specimens exhibited brittle failure after reaching maximum force. The close agreement between the curves suggests uniform fiber distribution and good reproducibility of the manufacturing process.

The tensile tests show a consistent linear-elastic behavior across all samples up to failure, with fracture forces ranging from approximately 170 MPa to 270 MPa. The elongation at break lies between 1.1% and 1.7%, indicating a brittle fracture behavior typical for fiber-reinforced thermosetting composites. The variation in fracture force may result from local differences in fiber distribution or matrix-fiber interaction quality.

The combination of high cure conversion, stable fiber volume content, low porosity, and consistent mechanical performance confirms the quality and reliability of the produced CFRP laminates.

Overall, UV curing demonstrates significant promise as a fast and energy-efficient alternative to thermal curing in composite manufacturing. The reduced curing time, combined with lower energy demand and the use of LED technology, supports the potential for more sustainable and scalable production of fiber-reinforced composites.

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REFERENCES

- [1] Karl-Heinz Füller: “Performance carbon fiber rear wall concept for the Mercedes-AMG S-Class”: In JEC composite magazine 110, 2017.
- [2] Heudorfer, K., Carosella, S., and Middendorf, P: “Nasspressen als Alternative zum RTM “: 25. Stuttgarter Kunststoffkolloquium, den 22.03.- 23.03.2017.
- [3] Schürmann, 2007; Lengsfeld et al., 2020
- [4] Zhilyaev, Igor; Brauner, Christian; Queloz, Sawsane; Jordi, Hans; Lüscher, Rolf; Conti, Silvio; Conway, Roy (2021): Controlled curing of thermoset composite components using infrared radiation and mathematical modelling. In *Composite Structures* 259, p. 113224. DOI: 10.1016/j.compstruct.2020.113224.
- [5] Rosenberg, P.: Entwicklung einer RTM Prozessvariante zur kavitätsdruckgeregelten Herstellung von Faserverbundstrukturbauteilen. Stuttgart 2019.
- [6] Faserverbundbauweisen. Fertigungsverfahren mit duroplastischer Matrix. Berlin, Heidelberg 1999.
- [7] Carosella, Stefan; Hügle, Sebastian; Helber, Florian; Middendorf, Peter (2024): A short review on recent advances in automated fiber placement and filament winding technologies. In *Composites Part B: Engineering* 287, p. 111843. DOI: 10.1016/j.compositesb.2024.111843.
- [8] Allnex GmbH. (2024) Technical data sheet RAYLOK ® C1100, Drogenbos, Belgium
- [9] Heudorfer, K.; Bauer, J.; Caydamli, Y.; Gompf, B.; Take, J.; Buchmeiser, M. R.; Middendorf, P.: Method of Manufacturing Structural, Optically Transparent Glass Fiber-Reinforced Polymers (tGFRP) Using Infusion Techniques with Epoxy Resin Systems and E-Glass Fabrics. In: *Polymers* 15 (2023) 9. <https://doi.org/10.3390/polym15092183>